

FIC Fighters

FIC-FIGHTERS Deliverable D7.1

Gender guidelines

Summary:

This deliverable presents the consortium's first gender analysis, contextualising global and European trends, summarising baseline findings, and specifying actionable steps for the full 48-month project period.

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1 Executive summary

Deliverable D7.1, Gender guidelines, is developed under Task 7.3 – Gender Analysis and Recommendations, within Work Package 7 (Project Management). The task, led by the University of Huelva (UHU) with contributions from all partners, aims to ensure that gender considerations are effectively integrated throughout the FIC-Fighters project. Its objective is to identify potential gender inequalities in project-related processes and decision-making, and to provide recommendations that promote gender balance, inclusivity, and equal opportunities at all levels of project implementation.

The analysis of gender aspects in research and innovation projects is still not a common practice, particularly in industrial initiatives such as FIC-Fighters. This deliverable presents the consortium’s first gender analysis, contextualising global and European trends, summarising baseline findings, and specifying actionable steps for the full 48-month project period. It draws upon survey responses and qualitative inputs collected from all partners to identify resource gaps, policy inconsistencies, and areas for targeted improvement.

The document concludes with practical recommendations designed to embed gender equality principles across organisational, project, and individual dimensions—reinforcing the consortium’s commitment to responsible research and innovation (RRI) and contributing to the excellence, inclusiveness, and societal impact of the FIC-Fighters project.

2 Introduction

2.1 The global situation

“How can we expect women to work and progress in their careers when they spend an average of four hours per day on unpaid care and domestic work (and up to seven hours in some countries), compared with just one and a half hours spent by men? Is it fair that women earn 15 percent less than their counterparts (in 2021) while doing the same type of job with the same set of skills? There is no positive outlook as since 2006 the gender pay gap has been reduced by only a few percentage points” (2023 UNESCO’s gender-based resilience report).

Within this negative general working environment, the research and innovation field is not performing better in terms of gender. The underrepresentation of women in science is a persistent global challenge with profound implications for scientific excellence, economic growth, and social equity and resilience. It goes against art.27 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UN,1948) that states **it is everyone’s right to share in scientific advancement and its benefits** and the 2017 UNESCO Recommendation on Science and Scientific Researchers encourages member states to promote supporting policies to include more women in the research community.

However, **only 33,7% of the global researchers are women¹**, and this share is lower in research areas developing social disruptive technologies such as **Artificial Intelligence, thus, the risks of reproducing gender and diversity biases increase exponentially** (UNESCO, 2024).

The situation is even more acute in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics **(STEM) fields- core of the FIC-Fighters project- where global female graduates are 35% (UNESCO, 2025) and their representation in research careers can fall below 20%.**

This scarcity is compounded by a **"leaky pipeline"** phenomenon, where the proportion of women decreases at each successive career stage. Women hold only 12% of memberships in national science academies and **face bigger significant barriers in securing research grants and publishing in high-impact journals, what impact heavily in their career’s stability and progression.**

Besides higher precarity rates, women and other underrepresented groups² face additional barriers in the workplace due to ambiguous causalities created by intersectionalities (i.e, ethnicity, social status or career stage, contract type/mobility, origin, language, sexual orientation) that worsen their chances to obtain, retain and get promoted in a job position.

¹ Based on headcounts from 95 reporting countries- UNESCO (2024), *The Gender Gap in Science*

² Women, LGBTQ+, ethnic minorities, migrants, people with disabilities and socially disadvantage groups among others.

Finally, data on sexual harassment at STEM workplace is almost inexistent and there is almost no research on their impact in women ´s career retention, progression or abandon. Alarmingly, a 2022 **UNESCO report indicates that one in two female scientists has experienced sexual harassment at work.**

This combination of numerical underrepresentation, career retention and progression barriers, heavier caring responsibilities and unsafe working environments constitutes a significant systemic failure, limiting the diversity of perspectives needed to drive excellency, creativity and societal impact of research and innovation.

2.2. The European context

Europe has advanced gender equality frameworks, but women´s representation among researchers has not uniformly improved. In **Central and Eastern Europe**, the share of women researchers **declined from 40.5% (2011) to 38.7% (2021)**, whereas in **Western Europe** it **rose from 31.8% to 33.9%** over the same period. These contrasting trends underscore the need for **targeted, context-specific measures** to achieve parity and sustain progress across regions.

Notes: Since 1996, 41 of the 42 countries in Europe reported the share of female researchers. Data source: UNESCO Institute for Statistics, January 2024

Figure 1. Female researchers as percentage of total researchers (HC), 2021 or latest year available

The *She Figures 2021* report reveals that **a higher proportion of women researchers work part-time and under precarious contracts (11.1% for women vs. 7.2% for men in higher education)**, a trend exacerbated at early career stages and for care givers.

The European Commission has responded with the *Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025* articulates a vision of a Europe in which all women and men, girls and boys, in all their diversity, are free to pursue their chosen path in life, are given equal opportunities to thrive and participate in – and lead – society. It identifies three inter-linked priority dimensions: (1) being **free from violence and stereotypes**; (2) thriving in a **gender-equal economy** (including closing pay and pension gaps, increasing women’s labour market participation and equal access to decision-making); and (3) **leading equally throughout society** (e.g., in politics and governance). The strategy emphasises a dual approach: combining gender-**mainstreaming** across all EU policies and programmes with **targeted actions** to address persistent gender-based inequalities, underpinned by an intersectional perspective that looks at how gender intersects with other axes of discrimination.

In relation to research and innovation (R&I), the strategy signals that gender equality is not simply a standalone social objective but a core element of research excellence, innovation relevance and competitiveness. In this line, the strengthening of the integration of the gender dimension into R & I is one of the gender equality priorities set for Horizon Europe, as integrating sex and/or gender analysis into research and innovation:

- adds value to research in terms of excellence, creativity and business opportunities;
- helps researchers and innovators question gender norms and stereotypes, and rethink standards and reference models;
- leads to an in-depth understanding of diverse gender needs, behaviours and attitudes;
- addresses the diverse needs of citizens of the European Union and thereby enhances the societal relevance of the knowledge, technologies and innovations produced;
- contributes to the production of goods and services better suited to new markets.

For **industry and industrial partners** this means that gender-responsive research involves designing technologies, products, processes and business models with attention to how sex, gender and diversity shape both user needs and operating contexts — **thereby improving research quality, social responsibility and market relevance**.

Under the framework of the *Horizon Europe (2021–2027)* and the broader *European Research Area (ERA)*, the integration of a gender dimension into project content is standardised: public research organisations applying for funding must have a Gender Equality Plan (GEP) in place, gender balance is a criterion for selection and evaluation panels, and the gender dimension must be addressed in research design and innovation uptake. Despite Horizon Europe GEP mandates, **only 11% of women in academia enjoy stable contracts** (*She Figures 2021*).

Despite these requirements, the effective translation of gender equality policies into practices remains inconsistent and challenging and there is a clear lack of monitoring, evidence and practical tools to effectively mainstream gender in research and innovation projects, particularly in industrial fields as the FIC-Fighters project.

As a consequence, a critical risk is **"gender washing"**, the practice of making superficial or symbolic efforts toward gender equality without implementing substantive, structural change. This is characterised by the production of policies that are very visible and publicly available but not actively communicated or implemented at the organizational level, missing dedicated resources, roles and expertise, and an absence of accurate monitoring and accountability mechanisms to track impact of them.

On the contrary, **gender mainstreaming**, involves assessing the implications for women and men of any planned action, and programmes, in all areas and at all levels. It requires a cultural shift from viewing gender as a standalone "women's issue" to integrating a gender perspective into the very fabric of an organization's culture, processes, and outputs and requires a big commitment and effort from all levels of the organizational structure and governance systems.

For an industrial perspective within the project, the business case is clear. Diverse teams are more innovative and better at problem-solving, adapting to all market needs and targets. A 2017 study by the Boston Consulting Group³ found **that companies with more diverse management teams have 19% higher innovation revenues (see figure below).**

Figure 2. Diversity and innovation relation

Furthermore, gender equality mitigates reputational risks, enhances a company's reputation and ability to attract and retain talent from the entire pool. It ensures that products and services are designed for a diverse user base, thereby accessing broader markets. Integrating gender is an imperative from a human right and ethical perspective. Moreover, it is a strategic element for industrial competitiveness and sustainable growth, and industry has a key role to play.

³ [How Diverse Leadership Teams Boost Innovation](#)

3 Objectives and rationale

FIC-Fighters is a Horizon Europe project focused on valorising phosphogypsum wastes into commercial products through sustainable and circular processes through a collaborative, multi-disciplinary approach. The project brings together 27 partners from academic institutions, research and technology organizations, civil society and local communities and industrial partners from across Europe. This diversity is a key strength but also presents a challenge for implementing a unified gender mainstreaming strategy, as partners operate under different national contexts, organizational cultures, and levels of pre-existing gender equality maturity.

The project recognizes that excellence in science and responsibility in innovation are two sides of the same coin. By proactively addressing gender equality, FIC-Fighters aims to:

- Enhance the creativity, quality, and societal relevance of its research and innovation outputs.
- Create a more inclusive, safe, and productive work environment for all staff and consortium members.
- Extract learnings and best practice for gender mainstreaming in industrial research.
- Contribute to the strategic gender goals of the European Research Area (ERA) and Horizon Europe.

As the project will not develop an industrial stage that would allow for the gender impact assessment and analysis in its implementation, the task leader proposed to fulfil a more general objective of increasing the awareness and knowledge of the consortium partners to enable the gender mainstreaming in a potential industrial phase and more generally, into their daily projects and actions. An initial gender analysis was performed to assess the departure situation and will be contrasted to a final one to assess progress.

In order to enable these extended objectives, a final survey will monitor the progress of consortium partners (as organizations, project and individuals) in gender awareness and gender equality capacities development.

Deliverable 7.1. Gender guidelines was moved from M12 to M18 and the duration of the related task (7.3. Gender analysis and recommendations) extended to cover the 48 months' full duration of the project assisting partners in the project and individual organization in gender aspects.

4 Methodology

4.1 Method´s description

The methodology employs a mixed-methods approach, combining an initial literature and project review as basis to develop a tailored three-levels survey covering the organizations, the FIC-Fighters project team and their individuals. The objective is to have a clear picture not only of the organizations in the consortium in terms of gender governance and gender practices/challenges but also of the underlying contexts and individual perceptions.

Taking into account the number and diversity of consortium partners, in terms of geographical coverage (from local to national or European); stakeholders types (from all Quadruple helix stakeholders: academia, industry, policy makers and civil society); cultural backgrounds, governance systems or national legal frameworks, the surveys (see Annexes) were carefully designed to include the full sample heterogeneity. They were initially tested by the project coordinator to assess the clarity and language use being understandable to all partners, industry in particular.

The surveys included definitions of the gender terminology used and the options proposed for the questions intended to raise awareness on potential actions and strategies to enhance gender equality and mainstreaming. Therefore, they were intended to collect data on the initial gender situation of the project but also to raise knowledge and awareness on challenges and potential interventions to address them. It was also thought **as a self-assessment tool** at the three above mentioned levels, as organizations can use it to assess their gender equality level and promote actions for improving it beyond the FIC-fighter project, or ideally, benefiting or complementing the project ones.

The surveys were presented and questions introduced in an online workshop on the 21st of February 2025 to all partners. The results and its analysis were presented and discussed on the 11th September 2025 to have partner´s feedback on the proposed actions - that are part of the gender plan in this document. They will be distributed again at the end of the project timeline to assess the evolution of both individuals and organizations. The rationale and main steps /timeline of the method are summarised in the table below.

Table 1. Summary of the methodology

General steps	Tasks	Schedule (months)
1. Measuring	Literature review: Gender Mainstreaming in project-level, industrial context	M6
	Preparing and applying a rapid measuring tool (1st check).	M8
	Designing data collection.	M8
	Data collection	M10-M48
	Data analysis	M10- M48
2. Assessing	Assessing and presenting data	M14- M46
	Elaborating GM strategy and action proposals	M18
	Discussing and prioritizing collectively GM strategy and action proposals.	M18
3. Acting	Developing actions to drive and improve GM.	M18-M44
4. Re-Assessing	Applying rapid measuring GM tool (2nd check)	M44
	Presenting results-all partners	M45
5. Learning	Final learnings and recommendations	M48

4.2 Development of Surveys

The literature and project review confirmed the lack of methods and tools for practical gender mainstreaming at the research project level, even less for industrial projects. As stated, Horizon Europe calls required Gender equality plans for public research organizations applying as coordinator, and many projects developed tools and guidelines to support the development of plans at the organizational level. However, at the project level there is a gap of models and guidelines on gender mainstreaming, and a bigger gap about private sector projects.

The gender surveys were tailored to the project specified requirements and based on the learnings from literature and project review, in particular D.2.2. SAGE survey (in the Annexes) and the [Gender Equality Audit and Monitoring \(GEAM\) tool](#). The individual survey also includes a standardised method from literature on perspectives and biases in the final set of questions.

Although very complete, both tools are targeting academic organizations or organizational units within public bodies, so the University of Huelva team did a full new version adapted to the variety of FIC-fighters' partners and the three levels (organizations, project and individuals) They consulted a broad number of articles and reports on gender mainstreaming (included in the gender digital library of the project in a shared platform) confirming the lack of literature and specific tools to industrial partners and STEM firms in particular, which are the core implementers at the project.

Therefore, upon the extension of these tasks until M48, the learnings of this unique exercise of gender analysis and mainstreaming will be disseminated to allow the uptake of similar interventions by other STEM firms. Tailored bilateral discussions and advise to partners will be offered during the project timeline to all FIC-Fighters consortium partners to support complementary measures and specific trainings for each organization needs.

Through the three surveys, the collection of questions intended to **cover most aspects of gender equality in partner's organizations**, providing high-quality data for designing and implementing gender equality measures and assessing their impact over the project time and beyond- as self- assessment tools to be iterative performed. The surveys can be used directly by the gender experts/roles in each organization for assessing the baseline situation and impact of equality measures over time and it can provide the basis for comparison among different sites (i.e. the multinational organizations or firms) of the same organization.

Figure 3. Intersectionality representation

The three-level survey (in the annexes) questions where complementary and double check key information as well as main intersectionality. They include:

- **Socio-demographic variables** questions that collect information sex and gender,
- **Working conditions** questions which collect information on the following: position in organization, academic field, net salary, bonus, faculty/ department, contract type, career access, progression, barriers and development training, caring

responsibilities, work role responsibilities, work and pay conditions and satisfaction levels, pregnancy support, work-family balance, leave support and workload.

- **Stereotypes, prejudices and bias** questions: collect information on unconscious bias, bias during recruitment, leadership.
- **Organizational culture and climate** questions collect information on representation of men and women, gender equality, differences in allocation of roles, promotions, treatment, perceptions of work environment and climate, recruitment factors, promotion factors, masculinity perceptions, team climate.
- **Interpersonal behaviours and experiences** questions collect information on micro aggressions, harassment, bullying and stalking, organizational workplace culture on bullying and harassment.

The surveys were specifically developed for each of the levels and addressed to respondents on a google form link to be filled in a maximum of 15 minutes and divided into:

1. The Organisational-Level Survey (OL) was composed by 22 questions and addressed to the gender expert or role in each of the 27 organisations in the consortium. It was completed by 22 (81%) organizations and covered institutional policies, resources, data monitoring, and work-life balance measures at the level of the whole organisation.
2. The Project Level (PL) survey was composed by 22 questions and targeted the project leaders in each organisation, principal investigators, project managers or focal points. It was completed by 25 project staff members (92% of response rate). It assessed the organization context and sensitivity of the specific team involved in the project.
3. The Personal level (PPL) survey was composed of 52 questions (10 -15 minutes completion time) and was sent to all 87 individuals in the project (including the project leaders targeted in the second survey). It was completed by 50 individuals, so the smallest response rate (57%). It assesses personal awareness, training, experiences with bias and harassment, perceptions of equality within the team, and societal views on gender from a personal perception.

The response rate was high for all surveys, except of the individual survey, indicating the high variations in terms of commitment, awareness and sensitivity of the project team but still, providing a robust and representative snapshot of the project's gender landscape at the M12 mark.

One important note is that the definition of the task is based on a binary gender perspective. As introduced earlier, a critical gap is the lack of data on intersectionality with LGTBIQ+ staff, precarity/contract type, professional scale, people with disabilities or caregiving responsibilities, or those from migrant or rural backgrounds. An intersectional approach, recognizing that these identities compound experiences of discrimination, is a necessary area for future development in line with the **gender +** conceptualization.

5 Analysis of Results

Data was analysed using a descriptive statistical analysis for quantitative data and the full excel with results anonymised. The results are structured across three levels of analysis (Organizational, Project, Personal) to provide a holistic gender analysis to develop recommendations for actions during the project timeline and beyond to the consortium partners.

The results and their interpretation were presented in an online gender analysis workshop held in September as mentioned earlier, with the participation of 24 attendants to reflect on the project departure point and ask for feedback on the proposed plan of actions (the PowerPoint is available in the annex). A summary of the main results by level is following.

5.1 Organizational Level: Structures, Policies, and Resources

The survey data reveals a consortium with positive intentions but significant structural weaknesses. Below the main results and graphical interpretation by category of questions.

Governance and Expertise:

Fewer than half of the organizations have a dedicated position for gender issues. Responsibilities often fall under general HR or diversity roles, leading to a dilution of focus. Critically, **only 22% of those responsible for gender feel they have sufficient resources, expertise, and time to perform their duties effectively.** This is a classic indicator of "gender washing" and a major barrier to meaningful action in the consortium organisations.

OL2. Your role in the organisation

21 respuestas

Figure 4. Percentage of Gender experts in partner´s organizations

OL2c. As a person in charge of gender, in your opinion, have you enough expertise and resources to perform its duties? Multiple responses

18 respuestas

Figure 5. Resources and training of gender experts

Policies and Communication:

While ~60% claim to have a Gender Equality Policy, and 70% a clear process to denounce sexual harassment or aggressions, its implementation is weak. Although 85% of these policies are publicly accessible, only 40% are actively communicated to new hires. There are virtually no specific incentives to hire or retain women, suggesting policies are passive rather than proactive.

SECTION 1- Gender institutional policy OL3. Does your organisation have a Gender Equality Policy or Plan?

21 respuestas

Figure 6. Percentage of organizations with Gender policy or plans

Representation and Data:

There is a clear leadership gap. Over 50% of organizations report a "Low" or "Very Low" ratio of women in executive committees and on the organization as a whole. Most of the organizations declare to take moderated (35%) or important (45%) measures towards

numerical parity but one in three organizations does not collect gender-disaggregated data by job level, making it impossible to accurately monitor parity progression or pay gaps. 86% declare that women and men are equally paid for the same work/role.

SECTION 2- GENDER DATA OL8. What is the ratio men-women in the Executive Committee or higher hierarchy?

21 respuestas

Vertical axis: number of responses; Horizontal axis: perceived ratio men/women
(1 = far fewer women ... 5 = parity/more women).

Figure 7. *Men/women ration in higher hierarchy*

OL10. What is the ratio men-women in the organization, as a whole ?

21 respuestas

Vertical axis: number of responses; Horizontal axis: perceived ratio men/women
(1 = far fewer women ... 5 = parity/more women).

Figure 8. *Men/women ration in the organization*

OL12. Is your organisation taking any measures towards gender parity or inclusion?

20 respuestas

Vertical axis: number of responses; Horizontal axis: Scale (1=little; 5=many)

Figure 9. Organisations taking measures towards parity or inclusion of women

Work-Life Balance and Culture:

40% of organisations lack a formal work-life balance policy. While flexible hours and telework are common, supportive measures like lactation rooms or financial support for maternity are rare (figure 11). A deeply concerning 40% of respondents perceive that taking carer's leave (e.g., maternity/paternity) is frowned upon in their organization, indicating a persistent cultural barrier.

SECTION 3- FAMILY CONCILIATION OL17. Has your organisation have a work-life balance policy formally recognised?

20 respuestas

Figure 10. Percentage of Family conciliation policies

The following options were proposed to answer the question “Does your organisation allow and support any of the following measures? (multiple choices)”, collecting the answers in Figure 11:

- Flexible working hours
- Telework
- Carer’s leave
- Sabbatical leave
- Study/training leave
- Extended maternity leave
- Extended paternity leave
- Breastfeeding time
- Breastfeeding facilities
- Incentives for external training/courses
- Family care allowance
- Mentoring programme (new/junior)
- Childcare/schooling support
- Informal exchange facilities
- Informal exchange & networking time
- Institution-wide core hours (e.g., meetings 10:00–16:00)
- Others

OL18. Does your organisation allow and support any of the following measures? (multiple choices):

21 respuestas

Figure 11. Most frequent Work-life conciliation measures

OL20. Would you say that carer's leave is frowned upon in your organisation?

21 respuestas

Figure 12. Perceptions on carer's leave

Two thirds of organisations monitor or keep track of sexual harassment cases although 85% declared none (of any kinds) was tracked in the last year. Regarding diversity and inclusion of other underrepresented groups (LGTBIQ+, migrants, people with disabilities, etc.) plans, 50% lack of them.

The following options were proposed to answer the question “Does your organisation monitor and keep track of sexual harassment cases? (multiple choices)”, collecting the answers in Figure 13:

- Yes of all kinds
- Non-verbal harassment
- None of them
- Others
- Sexual physical aggressions (as reported by victims)
- Verbal harassment (e.g., sexist comments or jokes)
- Gender discrimination (salary, promotion, responsibilities)
- Don't Know

OL21. Does your organisation monitor and keep track of sexual harassment cases? Multiple choices

21 respuestas

Figure 13. Monitoring of sexual harassment cases

5.2 Project Level: Team Dynamics and Work-Life Balance

At the project management level, there is a clear disconnect between policy and practice, as extracted from the summary of responses following. One important remark is that with 25 respondents to the survey (team leaders for each organisation) out of 27, **this was the highest response rate to all three surveys (92%)**.

Sensitivity and awareness:

About their perception on the gender sensitivity in their teams, it was considered as "moderate" but highly variable across organisations.

PL15. Would you say that your team in this project is gender sensitive?

23 respuestas

Vertical axis: number of responses; Horizontal axis: 1= very low- 5 = very high

Figure 14. Gender sensitivity perception by project leaders of each partner organization

Conciliation Measures:

Regarding work-life balance measures, 13% of project teams do not have the, neither formal or informally. Another significant negative finding is that 18% of teams report that "No one on the team can telework," excluding them from a basic work-life balance measure. This suggests inconsistent application of organizational policies at the project level and potential inequity between partners.

PL17. Has your project team have a work-life balance agreement/measures formally recognised?

23 respuestas

Figure 15. Work life balance measures

PL19. Is telework available to these staff groups contributing to FIC fighters? Multiple choices

22 respuestas

Figure 16. Telework possibilities by type of job

5.3 Personal Level: Awareness, Perceptions and Experiences

This is the most enlightening level as the survey was shared with **all individuals in the project and reflecting also in personal values and perceptions**, indicating the way for actions. Section 7- social perception- is the European Adaptation done by Charron and Alexander (2022) of the Modern Sexism Scale method. This level reveals a diverse workforce that is aware of gender inequalities and harassment as an issue **but lacks the knowledge, tools and confidence to address it.**

Figure 17. Respondents by organisation type

PPL3. Kindly indicate your gender

49 respuestas

Figure 18. Ratio of respondents by sex

Out of the 50 respondents of the total of 87 sample, 58% were women, indicating a gap of men (majority in the project) that did not commit during the 10- 15 minutes required to fill in the survey.

Awareness and Training:

We found out a moderated level of awareness on the existence of Gender institutional policies or plans- with 14% who does not know about their existence- and of anti-harassment policy or plans- with 26% who does not know if they exist for their own organisation. Moreover, 70% respondents indicated that there are gender policy at their organisations but only 54% indicated that measures against sexism are taken, showing an issue in the implementation of these policies.

PPL6b. If you replied yes, would you say your Gender Institutional Policy or Plan is well known by all the staff?

35 respuestas

Vertical axis: number of responses; Horizontal axis: perceived knowledge (1 = not at all ... 5 = very well known)

Figure 19. Perceived knowledge of gender policy/plan by staff

There is a critical training deficit as approximately 90% of FIC-Fighters staff have not received any gender-related training in the last year. These correlates with the relative ignorance of what to do in cases of witnessing/suffering physical sexual harassments cases and the 53% of respondents does indicate there is no gender role or expert or they do not know of their existence. An alarming 43% of respondents will not be clear on what to do if suffering or witnessing a physical sexual harassment. Strengthening practical, scenario-based training and visible roles and reporting pathways should be a priority across partners organisations.

PPL7. Would you know what to do if you suffer or witness any case of physical sexual harassment
 ? See definition in the introduction
 49 respuestas

Figure 20. Knowledge on protocols about physical sexual harassment

PPL11. Did you have any specific activity or training on gender in the last year?
 48 respuestas

Figure 21. Training activities in the last year

Conciliation measures

Almost 40% of the respondents are not sure that they could count on their teams support in case of need related to personal urgencies. Easy measures as institutional core working hours are modest in the organisations, with a positive answer in 60% of the respondents.

PPL22. Would you say that your project team promotes the share of job charges and responsibilities as to accommodate unplanned personal urgencies (family, child care, others)?

48 respuestas

Vertical axis: number of responses; Horizontal axis: 1=strongly disagree; 5=strongly agree
 Figure 22. *Team accommodates unplanned personal urgencies perception*

PPL23. Do you have core working hours (for instance, 10-16h) at the project level to enable family conciliation/ personal needs?

48 respuestas

Figure 23. *Core working hours implementation rate*

Team Dynamics and biases:

The existence of conciliation policy papers without supporting measures and transformation of rigid cultural context has no impact. The bad perception of parental leave is a big indicator of unconscious biases in this case to care givers, including women. The normalisation of extra hours (18% very often) or weekend work requests (10% very often) are clear signals of misalignment between policy and practice.

PPL13. Would you say that parental leave is frowned upon (badly perceived) in your organisation?

49 respuestas

Vertical axis: number of responses; Horizontal axis: 1=strongly disagree; 5=strongly agree

Figure 24. Parental leave perception

Only 20% of staff feel they can very often identify gender bias in others but less easy among themselves **with only 8,2% acknowledge perceiving differential treatment** between men and women. The same percentage that see clear differences in the career progression of men and women in their organisations. This suggests a normalization of subtle unconscious biases.

PPL28. Do you feel that you have gender biases (conscious or unconscious unequal treatment or perceptions towards women)?

49 respuestas

Vertical axis: number of responses; Horizontal axis: 1=not at all; 5= very much

Figure 25. Gender biases self-perception

In this line, 65% are certain gender doesn't influence career progression in their team, this leaves a **35% who are unsure or believe it does, in line with the 30% percentage replying they cannot assure men and women are equally paid for a same job.**

PPL20. Are men and women paid equally for the same job scale/role within the project team?

49 respuestas

Figure 26. Perception on pay gap between men and women

Gender Stereotypes:

14% of respondents showed doubts on the adequateness of women for STEM. The use of **gender-neutral language is very rarely or inexistent in 14%** of teams and only used commonly in 32% of them compared to the previous 6% of respondents have witness or suffered verbal harassment.

Although most respondents view “soft skills” as gender-neutral, subtle stereotypes persist. For example, **14% express doubts about women’s suitability for STEM roles,** and **46% associate “emotional intelligence and empathy” more with women.** These patterns point to **residual gender norms** that can influence recruitment, task allocation, and leadership opportunities unless addressed deliberately through **bias-aware practices and training.**

Societal Views and Underestimation of Discrimination:

A concerning proportion of staff underestimate structural gender issues. **Only 16% totally disagree (number 1) that “discrimination against women is no longer a problem in Europe”** and 34% would not agree on the statement that women miss out good jobs often due to discrimination. **10% of respondents totally agree and 20% more agree on the statement that “society has reached the point where women and men have equal opportunities for achievement”-** These replies indicate a need for awareness-raising on systemic and individual-level discrimination.

PPL42. Discrimination against women is no longer a problem in Europe

50 respuestas

Vertical axis: number of responses; Horizontal axis: 1=not at all; 2= I disagree; 3= I do not think so; 4= not sure; 5= I think so; 6= I agree; 7= I agree very much

Figure 27. Perception on gender discrimination

Besides the needs arising from the analysis of replies, a final question did enquire on concrete support from the gender expert in the FIC fighters team. **Training sessions (general and specific), access to training materials and organisation of the trainer of trainers workshops** were the most demanded actions. This reflects a personal interest in the subject as a first step to understand issues and change the mind-set of the team.

On a second level, the proposal of measures **involving individual´s organisations with corporate responsibility actions towards gender and family conciliation policy support as well as tailored advice** to i.e. the development of gender plans, policies and measures and monitoring and assessment tools were selected. The specific training to the hierarchy was the less selected measure.

The following options were proposed to answer the question “Would you be willing to be advised or supported anyhow by the FIC Fighters gender experts? (multiple choices)”, collecting the answers in Figure 28:

- General staff training
- Specific staff training
- Corporate responsibility actions
- Training materials & tools
- Others
- Train-the-trainer (GM, anti-harassment, biases)
- Tailored organisational advice (e.g., GEP / anti-harassment)
- Monitoring & assessment support
- Specific training for hierarchy/expert body
- Family conciliation policy support

PPL51. Would you be willing to be advised or supported anyhow by the FIC Fighters gender experts? Multiple choices

32 respuestas

Figure 28. Gender measures prioritization during the FIC-fighters project

5.4 Summary of Key Findings: SWOT

The FIC-Fighters consortium is at a crossroads. There is a foundational level of awareness and a desire to improve, but this is not yet supported by robust structures, adequate resources, or deep cultural change. The project performs marginally better than the average European organization in some aspects but exhibits clear signs of "gender washing" – having policies in place without the will or means to implement them effectively.

The main findings are summarised in a simplified SWOT analysis below:

Table 2. SWOT analysis

<p>Strengths:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High-level commitment to gender equality as a principle. - Good gender balance in overall project teams. - Existence of some GEPs and work-life balance measures in many partners organizations 	<p>Opportunities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use the Horizon Europe mandate as a catalyst for genuine change. - Leverage the diversity of the consortium for mutual learning. - Develop a model for gender mainstreaming in industrial research. - Improve innovation and societal impact through greater diversity.
<p>Weaknesses:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of dedicated resources and expertise for gender work. - Weak implementation and communication of existing policies. - Critical gap in gender training for staff. - Underrepresentation of women in leadership and persistent cultural biases. - Lack of systematic sex-disaggregated data collection. 	<p>Threats:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Resistance or inertia due to cultural differences and lack of time. - "Survey fatigue" leading to disengagement. - Superficial compliance (gender washing) without real impact. - Failure to address intersectional aspects of diversity.

6 Proposed Action plan

Based on the results of the survey, and discussions with the participants in the two gender sessions organised, the gender expert at the University of Huelva leading T.7.1. proposed an action plan that contributes to:

1. Embed Gender in Structures: Strengthen institutional capacity and policies for gender equality.
2. Cultivate an Inclusive Culture: Foster a project-wide culture of respect, inclusion, and safety.
3. Empower Individuals: Equip all staff with the awareness and skills to contribute to gender equality.
4. Mainstream Gender in Research: Explore the integration of a gender dimension in the project's R&I content.

As indicated the extension of this task until the end of the project will allow for continuous interaction with all the FIC fighters team as well as the individual organizations where they belong to as to work from both sides in the transition towards more equal, just, diverse and creative R&I industrial activities.

FIC-Fighters aims at being an inspiration to other similar projects and providing concrete tools and specific training within the industrial sector, that lack of clear guidelines and tools to mainstream gender and assess progress.

The proposed plan will be flexible to adapt to needs or requirement from the team and various stakeholder's types in the project, as well as able to provide tailored support to individual organisations requesting for it. **The project has done a first commitment to organize meetings and activities during core hours 10-16h in the last gender workshop.**

Table 3. Proposed Action Plan, with timeline and Key Performance Indicators (M18 - M48)

Phase	Objectives	Key Activities	KPIs
M18– M24	Build awareness	Launch OS Gender Library, 2 nd gender workshop	60% staff trained
M24– M30	Tailored training	Project Staff participating in a gender related training, discussion café or, Mutual learning session advisory sessions with organisations	60% staff in at least 10% of the organisations
M30– M36	Training	Sexual Harassment training/cafe	60% staff
M36– M42	Assessment	Second survey	70% response
M40– M48	Evaluate progress Disseminate lessons	Updated report Journal paper or policy brief Interview or podcast	Updated D.7.1 1 written publication 1 media content

7 Risks assessment

Several potential risks could hinder the implementation of this Gender plan:

Table 4. Risks assessment

Risk	Mitigation
Low participation in workshops and events.	Personalised outreach (emails, direct contact), flexible scheduling, commitment from the coordinator (IDENER) and sector-tailored content
Resistance to exchange on gender actions among organizations due to cultural/national differences.	Customised training modules that are context-sensitive, emphasizing relevance to local challenges and adapted to the sector/interest/language of the target audience.
Limited resources for the online tool library	Shared responsibility across partners to include more, big pool of resources already uploaded by the gender expert and available in the MSTeams Task folder
Survey fatigue among participants	Design concise, focused surveys that can be used for self-assessment in the organizations; Only a final survey will be deployed. The rest of questions will be done during the gender sessions, i.e. mentimeter without further time impact on participants.

8 Conclusions and way forward

The FIC-Fighters project is uniquely placed to contribute to gender mainstreaming methodologies in industrial research and innovation.

Through structured actions such as workshops, tailored training, gender cafés, and the creation of a resource library, the consortium can ensure measurable progress in gender equity.

The final outputs—including survey analysis, policy recommendations, and a publication—will serve as a significant contribution to EU-level discourse on gender in STEM and business.

By integrating these measures throughout the project lifecycle, FIC Fighters will not only meet its commitments but also leave a sustainable legacy of enhanced gender awareness and equity practices in research and business contexts.

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Annexes

- D.2.2. SAGE survey
- Organizational Level Survey questions and results (Detailed Charts)
- Project level survey and Results
- o Personal Level Survey Results (Detailed Charts)

template

Description of Deliverable 2.2 as per SAGE Grant Agreement: “Guidelines will be developed for the conduct of audits of internal procedures and practices, to identify any existing gender bias at the organisational level”.

Each SAGE partner conducted a gender impact assessment/audit of internal procedures and practices to identify gender best practices at organisational level. The analysis included data on Institutional Governance (including policies and practices), Career Progression, Work-Life Balance, and EnGendering Knowledge. This information will: identify critical gaps and challenges; assess the level of resources allocated to gender activities; establish the baseline for possible improvements and innovations, and feed into the design of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs).

	Yes	No	Partially	Don't Know
A. Institutional Governance				
A.1 Does the University have a policy on gender equality/diversity?				
A.2 If yes, where is this accessible (e.g. the University's website, policy booklet, etc.)? _____				
A.3 Is gender equality integrated into the University's objectives (e.g. Strategic Plan)?				
A.4 Does the University have a LGBTQI+ ⁴ Policy?				
A.5 If yes, where is this accessible (e.g. the University's website, policy booklet, etc.)? _____				
A.6 Is there a working plan or roadmap to achieve gender equality for the university?				
A.7 If yes, where is this accessible (e.g. the University's website, policy booklet, etc.)? _____				
A.8 Does the University's annual budget include provision for the promotion of gender equality? (e.g. budget to organize activities on gender-related issues, funding to research on gender, child care facilities or subsidies)				
A.9 Does the University have a policy to combat bullying and harassment?				
A.10 If yes, where is this accessible (e.g. the University's website, policy booklet, etc.)? _____				
A.11 Are there institutional activities to counteract or prevent sexual harassment and gender discrimination (e.g. information campaign, contact persons)?				
A.12 If yes, please elaborate: _____				

⁴ Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer and Intersex +

	Yes	No	Partially	Don't Know
A.13 Is training (e.g. on unconscious bias) available to staff to prevent and combat gender discrimination and sexism?				
A.14 If yes, (i) to whom is this targeted? _____ (ii) is this training obligatory for members of interview panels, or other recruitment/promotion roles?				
A.15 Is attention given to gender-sensitive language and images in all University official documents and on the University website? (e.g. does the university have guidelines or principles on gender-sensitive communication?)				
A.16 If so, give a brief overview: _____ _____ _____				
A.17 Are gender pay gap audits conducted?				
A.18 If yes, how often? Please elaborate _____ _____ _____				
A.19 Are members of recruitment, selection and promotion panels required to undergo equality training or awareness?				
A.20 If yes, how is this conducted? Please elaborate _____ _____ _____				
B. Engendering Knowledge				
B.1 Are there courses on gender at undergraduate level?				
B.2 Are there courses on gender at postgraduate level?				

	Yes	No	Partially	Don't Know
B.3 Does the University have a research centre(s) that focuses on gender equality or related activities?				
B.4 If yes, please name/list the centre(s)				

B.5 Does the University allocate financial resources to promote gender in the curriculum?				
B.6 If yes, please elaborate				

B.7 Does the University organise events relating to gender equality (e.g. International Women's Day)?				
B.8 Are staff members rewarded for or encouraged to engage in activities to advance/promote gender equality?				
B.9 If yes, please elaborate				

B.10 Are any initiatives in place to encourage women to take leadership roles in research (e.g. by applying for ERC funding?)				
B.11 Are researchers required or encouraged to include gender dimensions in research projects?				
C. Career Progression				
C.1 Is recruitment monitored to provide gender disaggregated data on applications/short-listing/appointments outcomes?				
C.2 Is promotion monitored to provide gender disaggregated data on applications/appointments outcomes?				
C.3 Does the University provide leadership training specifically for women?				

	Yes	No	Partially	Don't Know
C.4 Are there mentoring programmes for: i. early-career female researchers? ii. mid-career female researchers? iii. senior academic women?				
C.5 If yes, please elaborate _____ _____ _____				
D. Work Life Balance				
D.1 Does the University have a policy on work-life balance?				
D.2 If yes, where is this accessible (e.g. the University's website, policy booklet, etc.)? _____				
D.3 Does the University have a policy on maternity leave?				
D.4 If yes, where is this accessible (e.g. the University's website, policy booklet, etc.)? _____				
D.5 Does the University have a policy on paternity leave?				
D.6 If yes, where is this accessible (e.g. the University's website, policy booklet, etc.)? _____				
D.7 Does the University have a policy on parental leave?				
D.8 If yes, where is this accessible (e.g. the University's website, policy booklet, etc.)? _____				
D.9 Does the University have a policy on adoption leave?				
D.10 If yes, where is this accessible (e.g. the University's website, policy booklet, etc.)? _____				
D.11 Does the University have a policy on carer's leave?				

	Yes	No	Partially	Don't Know
D.12 If yes, where is this accessible (e.g. the University's website, policy booklet, etc.)? _____				
D.13 Does the University have a policy on sabbatical leave?				
D.14 If yes, where is this accessible (e.g. the University's website, policy booklet, etc.)? _____				
D.15 Does the University have a policy on flexible working?				
D.16 If yes, where is this accessible (e.g. the University's website, policy booklet, etc.)? _____				
D.17 Is there an institution-wide core hours (e.g. meetings scheduled between 10am and 4pm) policy to take account of caring/family/other responsibilities?				
D.18 If yes, please elaborate _____ _____ _____				
D.19 Is teleworking/telecommuting ⁵ available?				
D.20 Are there any support services or benefits available to staff with child caring responsibilities (e.g. workplace crèche, breast feeding facilities, baby-changing stations in both women's and men's toilets or separate toilet, subsidies for child care)? If Yes, please elaborate _____ _____ _____				
D.21 If yes, please indicate if any of these are accessible to women only _____ _____ _____				
D.22 Do you have further comments? If there are any other policies or practices you would like to highlight please do so here. _____ _____				

⁵ Teleworking and/or telecommuting refers to working remotely via internet, phone, etc. In the university context it may be defined as working a portion of contracted hours in the University and a portion at home.

FIC-FIGHTERS – Combined Gender Survey- Self assessment tool

How to Use This Pack

Purpose. This document consolidates the three official FIC-FIGHTERS gender surveys into a single, professional-grade file for external distribution: Organisational-level (OL), Project-level (PL), and Personal Perception-level (PPL). Estimated time: 10–20 minutes per respondent, depending on level.

Who should respond?

- Organisational level (OL): Gender focal point/HR or equivalent (one response per organisation).
- Project level (PL): Project Director/PI/Team Lead (one response per project team).
- Personal level (PPL): All people involved in FIC-FIGHTERS (one response per person).

How to answer. Tick all options that apply for multiple-choice items. For Likert questions select the number that best represents your view. “DK” = Don’t know; “N/A” = Not applicable.

Confidentiality & Data Protection. Responses are confidential and only reported in aggregate. Before distribution, replace the placeholders below with your local data-protection contact and retention policy. Ensure compliance with applicable law (e.g., GDPR).

For any comment: Contact juliana.chaves@uhu.es

Definitions & References for Respondents

Sexual harassment (Istanbul Convention, Art. 40). Any form of unwanted verbal, non-verbal or physical conduct of a sexual nature with the purpose or effect of violating the dignity of a person, in particular when creating an intimidating, hostile, degrading, humiliating or offensive environment. Examples include verbal (e.g., sexual comments or jokes), non-verbal (e.g., gestures, “elevator eyes”), and physical (e.g., unwanted touching).

Sexism. Beliefs about the fundamental nature and roles of women and men, often expressed as stereotypes or biases—conscious or unconscious—that can rank one gender as superior to another. Sexism can affect everyone, with women particularly impacted.

Gender & equality terminology. For multilingual definitions and standard wording, consult UN Women’s gender term bank. For institutional tools on sexism at work, see EIGE’s handbook.

Response Scales Used in these Surveys

- Agreement (1–5): 1 = Strongly disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neither agree nor disagree; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly agree.
- Knowledge (1–5): 1 = Not at all; 2 = Slightly; 3 = Moderately; 4 = Well; 5 = Very well known.
- Sensitivity (1–5): 1 = Very low; 2 = Low; 3 = Moderate; 4 = High; 5 = Very high.
- Perceptions (1–7): 1 = Strongly disagree ... 7 = Strongly agree.

A. Organisational Level Survey (OL)

To be filled by the gender expert/role in the organisation- aim to understand organisational policies and practices. For terminology, see UN Women Gender Term Bank; for tools, see EIGE “Sexism at Work” handbook.

Section 1 — Organisation & Role

OL1. Type of organisation

- Public Research Organisation / Public University
- Private Research Organisation / Private University
- Civil Society Organisation
- Local public administration
- National public administration
- Industry
- Other (specify)

OL1a. If “Other”, please describe:

OL2. Your role in the organisation

- Full-time Gender Expert
- Person in charge of gender (and other Departments as well)
- Other (specify)

OL2a. If you replied “Other”, please specify

OL2b. If you are the person in charge of gender, list the department(s)/themes

OL2c. Do you have sufficient expertise/resources to perform gender duties? (multiple responses)

- Yes, totally
- Partially — not enough training/expertise
- Partially — not enough budget
- Partially — not enough time/overloaded
- Partially — not enough staff support
- Not at all

Section 2 — Gender Institutional Policy

OL3. Does your organisation have a Gender Equality Policy/Plan (GEP)?

- Yes
- Partially
- No
- Do not Know (DK)

OL3a. If yes, is it publicly accessible (e.g., website)?

- Yes
- No

OL3b. If yes, include the link or describe where it is available

OL3c. Is the GEP well known by staff? (*Knowledge 1–5*)

OL3d. Is it shared with new staff entering the organisation?

- Yes
- No
- DK

OL4. Are there specific incentives for women to join the organisation?

- Yes
- No

OL4a. If yes, paste the link or describe briefly

OL5. Is there a clear process to denounce sexual aggressions?

- Yes
- No

OL5a. If yes, include the link or describe briefly

OL6. Is there a clear process to denounce sexual harassment?

- Yes
- No

OL7. Does your organisation have an anti-harassment policy/plan?

- Yes
- No

OL7a. If yes, include the link or describe briefly

Section 3 — Gender Data

OL8. Men–women ratio in Executive Committee / higher hierarchy (*1 = only men ... 5 = only women*)

OL9. Men–women ratio in Human Resources / recruitment (*1 = only men ... 5 = only women*)

OL10. Men–women ratio in the organisation (overall) (*1 = only men ... 5 = only women*)

OL11. Departments/sections with parity (or more women)? (*1 = none ... 5 = all of them*)

OL12. Is your organisation taking measures toward parity/inclusion? (*1 = none ... 5 = many measures*)

OL12a. If yes, list the most significant ones

OL13. How easy/hard is it to hire women in STEM? (*1 = very easy ... 5 = very hard*)

OL14. Do you regularly collect gender-disaggregated data at each job scale?

- Yes
- Partially
- No

OL15. Are remuneration/promotion decisions transparent? (*1 = not at all ... 5 = totally transparent*)

OL16. Are men and women paid equally for the same job scale/role?

- Yes
- No
- DK

Section 4 — Family Conciliation

OL17. Work-life balance policy formally recognised?

- Yes
- No

OL17a. If yes, share the link or explain briefly

OL18. Which measures are available? (select all that apply)

- Flexible working hours
- Telework
- Carer's leave
- Sabbatical leave
- Study/training leave
- Extended maternity leave
- Extended paternity leave
- Breastfeeding time
- Breastfeeding facilities
- Incentives for external training/courses
- Family care allowance
- Mentoring programme (new/junior)
- Childcare/schooling support
- Informal exchange facilities
- Informal exchange & networking time
- Institution-wide core hours (e.g., meetings 10:00–16:00)
- Other (specify)

OL18a. If "Other", describe briefly

OL19. Telework available to these staff groups (tick all that apply)

- Administrative
- Technical
- Commercial
- HR
- Higher hierarchy
- None of the staff can telework

OL20. Is carer's leave frowned upon in your organisation?

- Yes

- Partially
- No

Section 5 — Sexual Harassment & Discrimination

OL21. Do you monitor and keep track of sexual-harassment cases? (tick all that apply)

- Yes of all kinds
- Sexual physical aggressions (as reported by victims)
- Verbal harassment (e.g., sexist comments or jokes)
- Non-verbal harassment
- Gender discrimination (salary, promotion, responsibilities)
- None of them
- Others
- DK

OL21a. If “Others”, describe

OL22. Are you aware of any sexual-harassment case in the last year? (tick all that apply)

- Sexual physical violence or aggression
- Verbal harassment (incl. sexist jokes without any woman present)
- Non-verbal harassment
- Gender-discriminatory actions/processes
- No
- Others

OL22a. If “Others”, describe

OL23. Measures against sexism/sexist comments — describe briefly

OL24. Activities last year to prevent harassment/sexism/gender discrimination (tick all that apply)

- Internal GE training
- External GE training
- Code of Ethics and good conduct
- Online GE training
- Non-discriminatory language training
- Gender-disaggregated data
- Gender mainstreaming guidelines
- Discussion cafés
- Gender-bias awareness campaign
- Gender-related surveys/assessments
- Others

OL24a. If “Others”, specify

OL25. Diversity & inclusion policy/plan (e.g., LGBTBI+, disabilities, migrants)?

- Yes

- Partially
- No

OL25a. Link or description

OL26. Any national/international gender certification?

- Yes
- No
- DK

OL27. Would you welcome support from FIC-FIGHTERS gender experts? (tick all that apply)

- General staff training
- Specific training (staff/hierarchy)
- Training materials & tools
- Train-the-trainer (GM, anti-harassment, biases)
- Monitoring & assessment support
- Corporate responsibility actions
- Family conciliation policy support
- Tailored organisational advice
- Others

OL28. Other comments or requirements

B. Project-Level Survey (PL)

To be filled by the FIC-FIGHTERS Project Director/PI for each partner organisation in the project.

Results anonymised for initial gender assessment. Any comments please contact:

juliana.chaves@uhu.es

Section 1 — Your Profile

PL0. Your organisation's name (internal use only — anonymised)

PL1. Type of organisation

- Public Research Organisation / Public University
- Private Research Organisation / Private University
- Civil Society Organisation
- Local public administration
- National public administration
- Industry
- Other

PL1a. If "Other", describe

PL2. Your principal role in the organisation

- Researcher/academic
- Technician (lab/support)
- Administrative/finance/HR
- Commercial (clients/marketing/providers)
- Directive position (department/group lead)
- Other

PL2a. If "Other", specify

PL2b. If you are related to gender advice/services, briefly describe your tasks

PL3. Gender

- Man
- Woman
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to say
- Others

PL3a. If "Others", specify

PL4. Years in the organisation (for this project)

PL5. Contract type

- Staff permanent contract
- Staff temporary (linked to project)
- Subcontracted services for the project
- External consultant

- Stagiaire/practices
- Other

PL5a. If “Other”, specify

Section 2 — Gender Institutional Support

PL6. GEP in your organisation?

- Yes
- Partially
- No
- DK

PL6a. Is the GEP well known by staff? (*Knowledge 1–5*)

PL6b. Is it shared with new staff?

- Yes
- No
- DK

PL7. Any incentives for joining women?

- Yes
- No
- DK

PL8. Clear process to denounce sexual aggressions?

- Yes
- Partially
- No
- DK

PL9. Anti-harassment policy/plan?

- Yes
- Partially
- No
- DK

Section 3 — Gender Data (FIC-FIGHTERS Team)

PL10. Men–women ratio in the selection committee (*1 = only men ... 5 = only women*)

PL11. Men–women ratio in the project team (overall) (*1 = only men ... 5 = only women*)

PL12. Are you taking measures toward parity/inclusion?

- Yes
- No

PL12a. If yes, describe them

PL13. Ease/difficulty of hiring women with STEM profiles (1 = very easy ... 5 = very hard)

PL14. Do you collect gender-disaggregated data for this project?

- Yes
- Partially
- No
- Not applicable

PL15. Is your team gender sensitive? (Sensitivity 1–5)

PL16. Equal pay for the same scale/role within the team?

- Yes
- No
- DK

Section 4 — Family Conciliation

PL17. Work-life balance agreement/measures formally recognised?

- Yes
- Partially
- Not formally, but informally
- Not formally nor informally

PL17a. If yes, describe briefly

PL18. Team benefits (tick all that apply)

- Flexible working hours
- Telework
- Carer's leave
- Sabbatical leave
- Study/training leave
- Extended maternity leave
- Extended paternity leave
- Breastfeeding time
- Breastfeeding facilities
- Incentives for external training/courses
- Family care allowance
- Mentoring programme (new/junior)
- Childcare/schooling support
- Informal exchange facilities
- Informal exchange & networking time
- Institution-wide core hours (e.g., 10:00–16:00)
- Others

PL18a. If “Others”, describe briefly

PL19. Telework available to these staff groups (tick all that apply)

- Administrative
- Technical
- Commercial
- Human Resources
- Higher hierarchy
- None of the staff can telework

PL20. Diversity & inclusion policy/plan?

- Yes — the organisation has one
- Partially — covered by another plan
- No
- DK

PL21. Gender certification (e.g., Athena SWAN)?

- Yes — certified
- Partially — on process
- No
- DK

PL22. Other comments or assistance needs

C. Personal Perception-Level Survey (PPL)

To be filled by all individuals involved in FIC-FIGHTERS to assess personal knowledge and perceptions. Results are anonymised; use for initial gender assessment.

Section 1 — Your Profile

PPL0. Your organisation's name (internal use only — anonymised)

PPL1. Type of organisation

- Public Research Organisation / Public University
- Private Research Organisation / Private University
- Civil Society Organisation
- Local public administration
- National public administration
- Industry
- Other

PPL1a. If "Other", describe

PPL2. Your principal role in the organisation

- Researcher/academic
- Technician (lab/support)
- Administrative/finance/HR
- Commercial (clients/marketing/providers)
- Directive position (department/group lead)
- Others

PPL2a. If "Other", specify

PPL2b. If you provide gender advice/services, briefly describe your tasks

PPL3. Gender

- Man
- Woman
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to say
- Others

PPL3a. If "Others", specify

PPL4. Years in the organisation (for this project)

PPL5. Contract type

- Staff permanent
- Staff temporary (project-linked)
- Subcontracted for the project
- External Consultant
- Stagiaire/practices

- Other

PPL5a. If “Other”, specify

Section 2 — Your Organisation

PPL6. Does your organisation have a GEP?

- Yes
- Partially
- No
- DK

PPL6b. If yes, is it well known by staff? (*Knowledge 1–5*)

PPL7. Would you know what to do if you suffer/witness physical sexual harassment?

- Yes
- Partially
- No
- DK

PPL8. Anti-harassment policy/plan exists?

- Yes
- Partially
- No
- DK

PPL9. Gender role/expert exists?

- Yes
- No
- DK

PPL10. Enough measures against sexism and sexist comments?

- Yes
- No
- DK

Section 3 — Training

PPL11. Any gender-related training in the last year?

- Yes
- No

PPL11A. If yes, specify topics (e.g., gender mainstreaming, neutral language, biases, diversity)

Section 4 — Work Conditions & Conciliation

PPL12. Which measures did you use last year? (tick all that apply)

- Flexible working hours
- Telework
- Carer's leave
- Sabbatical leave
- Study/training leave
- Extended maternity leave
- Extended paternity leave
- Breastfeeding time
- Breastfeeding facilities
- Incentives for external training/courses
- Family care allowance
- Mentoring (new/junior recruits)
- Childcare/schooling support
- Informal exchange facilities
- Informal exchange & networking time
- Institution-wide core hours (e.g., 10:00–16:00)
- Others

PPL13. Parental leave is frowned upon in my organisation (*Agreement 1–5*)

PPL14. Organisation devotes adequate resources to deal with sexual violence/harassment (*Agreement 1–5*)

PPL15. My project team is gender sensitive (*Sensitivity 1–5*)

PPL16. STEM is adequate for women (*Agreement 1–5*)

Section 5 — Team & Equality

PPL19. Men–women ratio in your FIC-FIGHTERS project team (*1 = only men ... 5 = only women*)

PPL20. Equal pay for same scale/role within the team?

- Yes
- No
- DK

PPL21. Telework availability to all team members (*1 = never ... 5 = always*)

PPL22. Team shares duties to accommodate unplanned personal urgencies (*1 = not at all ... 5 = always*)

PPL23. Core working hours at project level (e.g., 10:00–16:00)?

- Yes
- No

PPL24. Required to work extra hours (*1 = never ... 5 = very often*)

PPL25. Need to work on weekends (*1 = never ... 5 = very often*)

PPL26. Team uses gender-neutral language (including informal spaces) (1 = rarely ... 5 = always)

PPL26a. In the last year, did you witness/suffer any of the following? (tick all that apply)

- Sexual physical aggressions
- Verbal harassment (e.g., sexist comments or jokes)
- Non-verbal harassment (looks, images, messages)
- Gender discrimination (salary, promotion, responsibilities)
- None of them
- Others
- DK
- Prefer not to reply

PPL26B. If yes, were they reported to the gender role/expert?

- Yes
- No
- DK

PPL26C. If reported, was the response effective? (1 = not at all ... 5 = yes, totally)

PPL27. I can identify gender bias in others (1 = never ... 5 = very often)

PPL28. I hold (conscious or unconscious) gender bias (1 = never ... 5 = very often)

PPL29. Women and men have the same voice/consideration in my team (1 = not at all ... 5 = yes, the same)

PPL30. Gender distinction is made in task assignment in the project (1 = never ... 5 = quite often)

PPL31. There are differences in career progression for women and men in my organisation (1 = not at all ... 5 = definitely)

PPL31A. If yes, why? (free text)

Section 6 — Soft Skills & Social Perceptions

PPL32–PPL41. Soft skills: indicate if each is more associated with women, more with men, or gender-neutral

- More associated with women
- More associated with men
- Gender-neutral
- Prefer not to say

PPL42. Discrimination against women is no longer a problem in Europe (Perception 1 not at all–7 completely agree)

PPL43. Women often miss out on good jobs due to sexual discrimination (Perception 1–7)

PPL44. It is rare to see women treated in a sexist manner (Perception 1–7)

PPL45. On average, people in our society treat husbands and wives equally (Perception 1–7)

PPL46. Society has reached the point where women and men have equal opportunity for achievement (Perception 1–7)

PPL47. It is easy to understand the anger of women's groups in Europe (Perception 1–7)

PPL48. It is easy to understand why women's groups are concerned about limits to women's opportunities (*Perception 1–7*)

PPL49. Media/government show more concern than warranted by women's actual experiences (*Perception 1–7*)

PPL50. Any other information relevant to assess the initial gender state of your organisation or project team?

PPL51. Would you like support from gender experts? (tick all that apply)

- General staff training
- Tailored organisational advice (e.g., GEP / anti-harassment)
- Specific staff training
- Specific training for hierarchy/expert body
- Training materials & tools
- Train-the-trainer (GM, anti-harassment, biases)
- Monitoring & assessment support
- Corporate responsibility actions
- Family conciliation policy support
- Others

PPL52. Further suggestions or requests for assistance